

1,2,4-Triazoles as Potential Antibacterial Agents: Biological Screening, Molecular Docking, and ADME/T Prediction

R. Priyadarshini^{1*}, M. Alagarraja², D. Christopher Vimalson³, T. Umapoorani⁴, Naveen Yadav J. K.⁵, S. Vijayshree⁶, P. Gnanasekar⁷

¹Department of Pharmaceutical chemistry, United College of Pharmacy, Periyanaickenpalayam.

²Department of Pharmaceutical analysis, United College of Pharmacy, Periyanaickenpalayam.

³Department of Pharmaceutics, United College of Pharmacy, Periyanaickenpalayam.

⁴Department of Pharmacognosy, United College of Pharmacy, Periyanaickenpalayam.

⁵Department of Pharmaceutics, United College of Pharmacy, Periyanaickenpalayam.

⁶Pharm.D, United College of Pharmacy, Periyanaickenpalayam.

⁷Department of Pharmacognosy, United College of Pharmacy, Periyanaickenpalayam

ABSTRACT

One of the most important components with antibacterial activity is the heterocyclic a component found in many commercial drugs. By affecting the lipophilicity, polarity, and hydrogen bonding capacity of the molecule, the 1,2,4-triazole moiety might enhance the pharmacological, pharmacokinetic, toxicological, and physicochemical characteristics of different heterocycles. Two triazoles, 4-Amino 5-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,4-Triazole-3-Thione and 4-(2-hydroxybenzalidine)amine-5-(2-hydroxy)phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol, were assessed for their antibacterial potential in the current study. These experimental triazoles have already been created and described. Three steps were planned for the evaluation of these triazoles: docking studies against the enzyme enoyl ACP reductase, ADME/T prediction of experimental triazoles, and in vitro testing for antibacterial activity.

Keywords: 1,2,4-triazole, antibacterial activity, docking studies, ADME/T prediction, Enoyl ACP reductase

INTRODUCTION

Disease agents produce infection, which is the invasion of bodily organisms and can start in a small area and spread to the entire body ^[1]. Yeast, fungus, viruses, and bacteria are among the pathogens that can cause infections that are fatal ^[2]. A major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, bacterial infections are among the most prevalent infections in both hospitals and the general population ^[3,4]. The ability of antibiotics to stop the growth of pathogens makes them an effective treatment for bacterial illnesses ^[5,6]. Nevertheless, because of prolonged antibiotic misuse, microorganisms have developed resistance to practically all antibiotics ^[7,8]. There is an urgent need to create new chemicals with strong antibacterial properties to address this problem ^[9,10]. The creation of new substances with potent antibacterial properties is urgent.

In contemporary drug research, the heterocyclic a component of many marketed medications is one of the most crucial elements with antibacterial activity. The 1,2,4-triazole moiety can improve the pharmacological, pharmacokinetic, toxicological, and physicochemical aspects of various heterocycles by influencing the molecule's lipophilicity, polarity, and hydrogen bonding capacity^[11,12]. The pharmacological characteristics of 1,2,4-triazole derived compounds often include antibacterial, antiviral^[15,16], antitubercular^[17,18], antifungal^[19,20], and anticancer^[13,14] effects, with a high level of antibacterial^[21,22] activity.

In current study we evaluated two triazoles i.e.4-Amino 5-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,4-Triazole-3-Thione and 4-(2-hydroxybenzalidine)amine-5-(2-hydroxy)phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (Figure 1) for their antibacterial potential. These experimental

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

triazoles were already synthesized and characterized in Pharmaceutical Chemistry Lab of United college of Pharmacy [23]. Evaluation of these triazoles was planned in three steps i.e. ADME/T prediction of

experimental triazoles, docking studies against Enoyl ACP reductase enzyme and finally by *In-vitro* evaluation for antibacterial activity.

Figure1: 3D structures of UI(A) and UIA.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE:

Physiochemical and ADMET property prediction:

Physiochemical properties of both lead molecules were determined by using virtual prediction tool FAF Drug3 server[24]. UI and UIA compounds were screened through molinspiration online tool in order to obtain their drug likeness characteristics. Rule of 5

also helps us to understand ADME/T properties of ligands. According to Rule of 5, ligand must carry following molecular characteristics in order to be considered as a drug molecule: Hydrogen Bond Donor ≤ 5 (OH and NH Groups), Hydrogen Bond Acceptor ≤ 10 (N and O atoms), molecular weight ≤ 500 Dalton and partition coefficient (Clogp) less than 5[25,26] (Figure 2).

Figure2: Different conformational positions of UI(A) and UIA(B) in the binding pocket of Enoyl ACP reductase as enzyme, exhaustiveness was set at 8.

Using the GUSAR model to estimate toxicity:

For each lead compound given by intravenous (IV), oral, subcutaneous (SC), and intraperineal (IP) routes, LD₅₀ values were predicted based on acute rat toxicity. Regarding the widely unrestricted structure activity relationship, the GUSAR paradigm [27].

Docking studies

Molecular modeling: Structures of both triazoles UI and UIA were drawn and cleaned into 3D models

using Marvin Sketch Tool and were saved in PDB formats[28] (Figure.1). Mol formats of both ligand molecules were converted into PDB files using Discovery Studio and were finally prepared into PDBQT file using PyRx tool in order to produce atomic coordinates. 3D crystal model of Enoyl ACP reductase enzyme (FabI) was acquired from Protein Data Bank (PDBID:1C14) (Figure 2). Using Drug Discovery Studio, Ramachandran Plots for the downloaded protein model. Ramachandran Plot tells about specific low energy conformations for ϕ (phi) and (psi) or stable conformations of amino acid

residues along with favorable and unfavorable regions for amino acid residues in plot. (Figure 3) Points on the plot indicate the ϕ (phi) and ψ (psi), the torsion angles of amino acid residues in a 3D protein model^[26]. Both target protein (FabI) and ligand were uploaded in BioLip Virtual Tool in order to find out the coordinates of ligand in original target protein site^[27]. BioLip is an online Ligand-Protein binding database used for prediction of ligand binding residues in a target protein.

Figure 3: 3D model of Enoyl ACP reductase built acquired from PDB (PDB ID: 1C14) and Viewed using Discovery Studio 4.1.

Docking run: The target-ligand interaction can be evaluated computationally using the docking method. The PyRx Virtual Screening tool, an Auto dock Vina option based on scoring functions, was used to upload the ligand and the target protein, FabI, in order to closely monitor and evaluate any possible residual

interaction between the two. Several interaction postures were observed utilizing Discovery Studio to evaluate the residual interaction of triazoles with the target enzyme^[28].

Antibacterial Susceptibility Testing

In vitro antibacterial susceptibility testing using the serial dilution method was used to determine the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values against *E. coli*^[29].

RESULTS

ADMET and physicochemical property prediction:

Predicted water solubility values (in mg/L) showed that UI had equivalent water solubility, which is defined as 31681.67 mg/LVs. 38565.40 mg/L instead. On the VEBER and EGAN models, UI and Triclosan demonstrated a favorable oral bioavailability profile. Triclosan and UIA together were projected to have a higher oral bioavailability than UIA, which had a solubility of 8704.71 mg/L (Table 1). Triazoles UI and UIA met the Rule of Five requirement without any violations. UI and UIA had molecular weights of 208 and 312 Dalton, respectively. Similarly, since all other pharmacokinetic parameters (ADME/T) for all lead molecules were within normal ranges with zero violations, both triazoles may be developed as therapeutic agents (Table 1).

Table1: Physico chemical properties/ADME prediction.

Physicochemical Properties	UI	UIA	Triclosan
Molecular Weight	210.25	312.34	306.27
logp	1.0	2.59	0.5
logD	0.92	3.35	0.56
log Sw	1.89	3.58	-2.07
Topological Polar Surface Area	76.90	83.52	81.65
Rotatable Bonds	1	3	5
Rigid Bonds	11	18	16
Flexibility	0.083	0.14	0.24
Hydrogen Bond Donor	4	2	1
Hydrogen Bond Acceptor	5	6	7
Rings	2	3	3
Max size ring	6	6	6
Num Charges	0	1	0
Total Charge	0	-1	0
Heavy atoms	14	22	22
Carbons Atoms	8	15	13

Hetero Atoms	6	7	9
Ration H/C	0.75	0.46	0.69
Lipinski Violations	0	0	0
Solubility mg/L	31681.67	8704.71	38565.40
Solubility Forecast Index;	Good	Reduced Solubility	Good Solubility
Oral_Bioavailability_VEBER	Good	Acceptable	Good
Oral_Bioavailability_EGAN	Good	Acceptable	Good

Using the GUSAR model to predict toxicity:

Both experimental triazoles were shown to be potentially nontoxic based on predicted LD₅₀ values (in mg/kg) via IV, oral, SC, and IP routes; as a result,

their toxicity profile in animal models can be further investigated^[30]. The GUSAR model for toxicity prediction also demonstrated that the LD₅₀ values of UI and UIA were similar to those of the reference standard Triclosan (Table 2).

Table 2: Rat acute toxicity values of selected ligand molecules using GUSAR.

Route of Administration	LD50mg/kg		
	UI	UIA	Triclosan
Intra-peritoneal	280,900	481,900	708,400
Intravenous	64,320	193,600	200,400
Oral	764,600	1,548,000	584,000
Subcutaneous	521,990	1,212,000	511,300

Supertoxic(<5mg/kg),extremelytoxic(5-50mg/kg),verytoxic(50-500mg/kg),moderatelytoxic(500-5000mg/kg),slightlytoxic(5000-15,000mg/kg),andpractically non-toxic (>15000 mg/kg) ^[30].

Docking studies

The internet server 3D Ligand Site was used to examine the binding site with the ligand's atomic

coordinates. Amino acids HIS, LEU, and ALA were found in the target enzyme FabI's active binding pocket (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4: A Ramachandran map was made using Drug Discovery Studio 4.1 to indicate if amino acid residues are in the "accepted region" or the "unaccepted" region. A good 3D protein model should have more than 90% of the amino acid residues in the desired Ramachandran Plot quadrant.

Figure 5: The amino acids HIS, LEU, and TYR are indicated in the Enoyl ACP reductase enzyme's binding pocket.

When both ligands were docked to the target protein (FabI), the lowest binding affinity values were discovered. According to this, the Ligand-Target combination is stable and capable of forecasting FabI inhibition in silico. Docking energies calculated using PyRx based on Autodock Vina were -7.8 and -5.9 Kcal/mol with favorable RMSD values, compared to -7.1Kcal/mol with reference standard Triclosan

(Table 3). The hydrogen bond donor and recipient regions of the ligand and target proteins, as well as the distance between the interacting atoms, were meticulously examined in our study. The intensity of the connection between the ligand and target protein is significantly predicted by their hydrogen interactions (Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6: (A) UI entrapped in the binding pocket of yeast enzymes with 3D positions with heat map (B) Residual interaction of atoms of UI with serine and tyrosine amino acids of bacterial enzyme in the binding pocket. OH group of ligand is interacting with amino acids at distance of 2.96 & 2.19Ao. (C) Two-Dimensional interaction patterns of UI with target enzyme.

Figure 7: (A) UIA entrapped in the binding pocket of bacterial enzymes how with 3D positions with Heat Map (B)Residual interaction of atoms of UIA with serine and amino acid, Histine 468 of bacterial enzyme in the binding pocket. OH group of ligand is interacting with amino acids at distance of 2.22Ao. (C) Two-Dimensional interaction patterns of UIA with target enzyme.

Table3: Following a ligand-target protein docking run, binding affinity energies and Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) values were collected.

Ligand-Target Complex	Binding Affinity	RMSD	RMSD
1C14_U1	-6.5	0	0
1C14_U1	-6.0	1.399	1.338
1C14_U1	-6.0	2.308	1.818
1C14_U1	-5.6	2.026	1.371
1C14_U1A	-7.4	0	1.338
1C14_U1A	-7.0	1.313	2.114
1C14_U1A	-6.1	2.491	3.925
1C14_U1A	-6.0	3.383	0
Triclosan- U1	-7.0	0	2.722
Triclosan- U1	-7.0	5.471	2.781
Triclosan- U1A	-6.9	5.625	3.290
Triclosan- U1A	-6.9	5.225	0

ANTI BACTERIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY TESTING

In-vitro antibacterial susceptibility testing that all bacterial strains including *E.coli* were susceptible to both experimental triazoles and with serial dilution method UIA showed better MIC values than UI (Table 4). UIA showed least MIC values against *E.col* I i.e., 24 μ g which unveils its promising potential as antibacterial agent and requires further investigation *in-in-vivo* models.

Table 4: Minimum inhibitory concentration values.

Organisms	MIC Values(μ g)		
	UI	UIA	Triclosan
<i>Escherichia coli</i> NCIM 2911	42	24	10

CONCLUSION

We propose UIA as an excellent inhibitor of Enoyl ACP reductase with comparable docking energy values with reference standard Triclosan because docking studies revealed that both lead triazoles, including UI and UIA, showed excellent binding

affinity values, especially the Lipinski Rule of Five was met by both lead molecules (UI and UIA) with zero violations, indicating that both ligand molecules are good therapeutic candidates. UIA showed the most stable ligand-target complex. When both experimental compounds were computationally investigated via IV, IP, SC, and oral routes of administration, rat acute toxicity prediction using the GUSAR model indicated that both were nontoxic. In vitro antibacterial susceptibility testing of both UI and UIA was used to validate docking results. The pathogenic bacterial strain was found to be susceptible to triazoles using antibacterial susceptibility testing. When compared to Triclosan against *E. coli*, UIA had even more encouraging MIC values. Additionally, insilico investigations offer an excellent framework for quickly and affordably screening small compounds for potential biological activity in a dry lab.

REFERENCES

1. L. Radlinski, B.P. Conlon, Antibiotic efficacy in the complex infection environment, *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.* 42 (2018) 19e24.
2. M.A. Hutnick, J.K. Pokorski, Polymeric interventions for microbial infections: a review, *Mol. Pharm.* 15 (2018) 2910e2921.
3. C.Gao, Y.L. Fan, F. Zhao, Q.C. Ren, X. Wu, L. Chang, F.Gao, Quinolone derivatives and their activities against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 157(2018)1081e1095.
4. F. Gao, P. Wang, H. Yang, Q. Miao, L. Ma, G.M. Lu, Recent developments of quinolone-based derivatives and their activities against *Escherichia coli*, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 157(2018)1223e1248.
5. H.Huse, M.Whiteley, 4-Quinolones, Smartphones of microbial world, *Chem. Rev.* 111(2011)152e159.
6. H.Guo, Isatin derivatives and their antibacterial activities, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 164 (2019) 678e688.
7. G. Dhanda, P. Sarkar, S. Samaddar, J. Haldar, Battle against vancomycin-resistant bacteria: recent developments in chemical strategies, *J. Med. Chem.* 62(2019)3184e3205.
8. Z. Xu, S.J. Zhao, Z.S. Lv, F. Gao, Y.L. Wang, F. Zhang, L.Y. Bai, J.L. Deng, Fluoro-quinolone-isatin hybrids and their biological activities, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 162(2019)396e406.
9. Gomtsyan, Heterocycles in drugs and discovery, *Chem. Heterocycl. Comp.* 48 (2012) 7e10.
10. S.E.Rossiter, M.H.Fletcher, W.M.Wuest, Natural products as platform to overcome antibiotic resistance, *Chem. Rev.* 117(2017)12415e12474.
11. P.Kaur, A. Chawla, 1,2,4-Triazole: a review of pharmacological activities, *Int. Res. J. Pharm.* 8(2017)10e29.
12. B.Kapron, J.J.Luszczki, A.Plaziska, A.Siwiek, T.Karcz, A.Grybos, G.Bowak, a. Makuch-Kocka, K.Walczak, E.Langner, K.Szalast, S.Marciniak, M.Paczkowska, J.Cielecka, L.M.Ciesla, T.Plech, Development of the 1,2,4-triazole-based anticonvulsant drug candidates acting on the voltage-gated sodium channels. Insights from in-vivo, in-vitro and in-silico studies, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 129 (2019)42e57.
13. S.A.Shahzad, M.Yar, Z.A.Khan, L.Shahzadi, S.A. R.Naqvi, A.Mahmood, S.Ullah, A.J.Shaikh, T.A.Sherazi, A.T.Bale, J.Kukulowicz, M.Bajda, Identification of 1,2,4-triazoles as new thymidine phosphorylase inhibitors: future anti-tumor drugs, *Bioorg. Chem.* 85 (2019) 209e220.
14. H.A.M.El-Sherief, B.G.M.Youssif, S.N.A.Bukhari, A.H.Abd elazeem, M.Abdel-Aziz, H.M.Abdel-Rahman, Synthesis, anticancer activity and molecular modeling studies of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives as EGFR inhibitors, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 156 (2018) 774e789.
15. K.Wittine, M.S.Babic, D.Makuc, J.Plavec, S.K.Pavelic, M.Sedic, K.Pavelic, P. Leyssen, J. Neyts, J. Balzarini, M. Nintas, Novel 1,2,4-triazole and imidazole derivatives of L-ascorbic acid: synthesis, anti-HCV and anti-tumor activity evaluations, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* 20(2012)3675e3685.
16. Kucukguzel, E.Tatar, S.G.Kucukguzel, S.Rollas, E.D.Clercq, Synthesis of some novel thiourea derivatives obtained from 5-[(4-aminophenoxy)methyl]-4-alkyl/aryl-2,4-dihydro-3H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones and evaluation as antiviral/anti-HIV and anti-tuberculosis agents, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 43(2008)381e392.
17. S. Zhang, Z. Xu, C. Gao, Q.C. Ren, L. Chang, Z.S. Lv, L.S. Feng, Triazole de-

- rivatives and their anti-tubercular activity, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 138(2017)5 01e513.
18. Z. Xu, S. Zhang, C. Gao, F. Zhao, Z. S. Lv, L. S. Feng, Isatin hybrids and their anti-tuberculosis activity, *Chin. Chem. Lett.* 28(2017)159e167.
 19. R. Y. Jin, C. Y. Zeng, X. H. Liang, X. H. Sun, Y. F. Liu, Y. Y. Wang, S. Zhou, Design, synthesis, biological activities and DFT calculation of novel 1,2,4-triazole Schiff base derivatives, *Bioorg. Chem.* 80 (2018) 253e260.
 20. Xu, Y. Cao, J. Zhang, S. Yu, X. Chai, Q. Wu, D. Zhang, Y. Jiang, Q. Sun, Design, synthesis and antifungal activities of novel 1,2,4-triazole derivatives, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 46 (2011) 3142e3148.
 21. S. Eswaran, A. V. Adhikari, N. S. Shetty, Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of novel quinoline derivatives carrying 1,2,4-triazole moiety, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 44(2009)4367e4647.
 22. Y. L. Fan, X. Ke, M. Li, Coumarin triazole hybrids and their biological activities, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.* 55(2018)791e802.
 23. Muhammad SA, Ali A, Ismail T, Zafar R, Ilyas U, et al. (2014) In silico study of anti-carcinogenic lysyl oxidase like 2 inhibitors. *Comput Bio Chem* 51: 71-82.
 24. Lagorce D, Sperandio O, Baell JB, Miteva M. A, Villoutreix BO (2015) FAF-Drugs 3: a web server for compound property calculation and chemical library design. *Nucleic Acids Res* 43: 200-207.
 25. Lipinski CA (2004) Lead and drug like compounds: the rule of five revolution. *Drug Discov Today Technol* 1:337-341.
 26. Pollastri MP (2010) Overview on the Rule of Five. *Curr Protoc* 9:2.
 27. Hassan M, Ashraf Z, Abbas Q, Raza H, Seo S. Y (2016) Exploration of Novel Human Tyrosinase Inhibitors by Molecular Modeling, Docking and Simulation Studies. *Inter discip Sci*: 1-13.
 28. Dunkel M, Günther S, Ahmed J, Wittig J, Preissner R (2008) Super Pred: Drug classification and target prediction. *Nucleic Acids Res* 36: 55-59.
 29. Hoof RW, C Sander, Vriend G (1997) Objectively judging the quality of a protein structure from a Ramachandran plot. *Comput Appl Biosci* 13: 425-430.
 30. Yang J, Roy A, Zhang Y (2013) Protein-ligand binding site recognition using complementary binding-specific substructure comparison and sequence profile alignment. *Bioinfo* 29:2588-2595.
 31. Dallakyan S, Olson AJ (2015) Small molecule library screening by docking with PyRx. *Methods Mol Biol* 1263: 243-250.
 32. Fothergill AW (2012) Antibacterial susceptibility testing: Clinical laboratory and standards institute (CLSI) methods. *Interactions of Yeasts, Moulds, and Antibacterial Agents*. Springer.
 33. Ruiz P, Begluitti G, Tincher T, Wheeler J, Mumtaz M (2012) Prediction of acute mammalian toxicity using QSAR methods: a case study of sulfur mustard and its break down products. *Molecules* 17: 8982-9001.

HOW TO CITE: R. Priyadarshini, Dr. M. Alagarraja, Dr. D. Christopher Vimalson, T. Umapoorni, Naveen Yadav J. K, Dr. S. Vijayshree, P. Gnanasekar, 1,2,4-Triazoles as Potential Antibacterial Agents: Biological Screening, Molecular Docking, and ADME/T Prediction, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (11), 471-478. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17589332>

